

Iterative Methods for Estimation of 2-D AR Parameters using a Data-Adaptive Toeplitz Approximation Algorithm

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Abstract

A new two-dimensional data-adaptive algorithm utilizing the iterative Toeplitz approximation method is presented. This algorithm provides a means for efficient estimation of 2-D AR parameters representing spatially variant data arrays. Its convergence performance is comparable to that of the 2-D Recursive Least Squares (RLS) algorithm but is computationally more efficient. The savings in computation is realized by reducing the size of the matrix to be inverted when solving the AR model normal equations. The ability of the algorithm to accurately estimate the model parameters using very small data sets and various windowing schemes are evaluated. Single quadrant and combined quadrant (CQ) spectral estimates are compared for quarter-plane (QP), and nonsymmetric half-plane (NSHP) regions of support.

1 Introduction

The traditional least squares or Wiener filtering based 2-D AR parameter estimation methods [1] provide accurate spectral estimates but require the inversion of a relatively large autocorrelation matrix. This is undesirable since matrix inversion is computationally expensive. Iterative methods, using a Toeplitz approximation algorithm, have been suggested [2, 3] as an alternative to the direct Wiener filter solution. The iterative Toeplitz approximation method has proven to be an effective means to estimate the parameters of fixed data arrays without having to invert the correlation matrix. This method is particularly useful when data arrays of limited size must be processed.

The results obtained using iterative methods to obtain the AR parameters of fixed data arrays suggest that these methods may be used to some advantage when estimating parameters adaptively. Adaptive parameter estimation is necessary in many digital

signal processing applications where the data is non-stationary. In these applications, real-time or near real-time processing is often desirable. This requires that any algorithm used must be computationally efficient and be capable of providing accurate estimates obtained from a minimum of data. This paper addresses the implementation of the iterative Toeplitz approximation method for 2-D parameter estimation of non-stationary data. It is shown that this algorithm can be efficiently implemented to obtain accurate estimates from very small data arrays.

2 Solving The Normal Equations by Direct Inversion

In the 2-D least squares problem, the error between the random process $x[n_1, n_2]$ and its estimate $\hat{x}[n_1, n_2]$ is given by

$$e[n_1, n_2] = x[n_1, n_2] - \hat{x}[n_1, n_2] \quad (1)$$

or in expanded form as

$$e[n_1, n_2] = x[n_1, n_2] + \sum_{(i,j) \in A} a(i, j)x[n_1 - i, n_2 - j], \quad (2)$$

for $(i, j) \neq (0, 0)$. The objective of the least squares method is to minimize the squared errors from a particular set of these terms [4]. If we let $a(0, 0) = 1$, we can express (2) as

$$e[n_1, n_2] = \sum_{(i,j) \in A} a(i, j)x[n_1 - i, n_2 - j] \quad (3)$$

which is compactly represented in vector notation as $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{a}$. The error $e[n_1, n_2]$ is computed for each position of the filter, then normal equations are formed by multiplying both sides of (3) by \mathbf{X}^T and applying the orthogonality principle [5]. This results in

$$\mathbf{R}\mathbf{a} = \mathcal{E} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ and the error variance vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{e} = [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(0)T}, 0, \dots, 0]^T$ with $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(0)} = [\sigma_\varepsilon^2, 0, \dots, 0]^T$. The parameter estimates are obtained from (4) by multiplying both sides of the equation by the inverse of \mathbf{R} . This is referred to as the *direct inversion method*.

3 Solving The Normal Equations using Iterative Methods

An alternative to direct inversion is to take advantage of the near Toeplitz-block-Toeplitz structure of the autocorrelation matrix and successively partition the normal equation [2]. This partitioning permits the estimation of parameters while requiring the inversion of a matrix that is significantly smaller than the original autocorrelation matrix. The following discussion develops the iterative solution for QP region of support.

In order to iteratively solve the QP normal equations we must begin by dividing both sides of (4) by σ^2 . This results in a modified normal equation given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_0 & \mathbf{R}_{-1} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{-P_1+1} \\ \mathbf{R}_1 & \mathbf{R}_0 & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{-P_1+2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}_{P_1-1} & \mathbf{R}_{P_1-2} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_0'' \\ \mathbf{a}_1'' \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{a}_{P_1-1}'' \end{bmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{R}_k are $P_1 \times P_2$ Toeplitz blocks of correlation terms, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = [100, \dots, 0]^T$ and $\mathbf{a}_i'' = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \mathbf{a}_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, P_1 - 1$. We now partition the normal equation (5) to form an iterative solution. We can combine the resulting iterative solutions from the successive levels of partitioning into a set of compact iterative summations

$$\mathbf{a}_0''^{(k)} = \mathbf{a}_0''^{(0)} - \mathbf{R}_0^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{P_1-1} \mathbf{R}_{-i} \mathbf{a}_i''^{(k-1)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_j''^{(k)} = -\mathbf{R}_0^{-1} \sum_{i=0}^{P_1-1} \mathbf{R}_{j-i} \mathbf{a}_i''^{(k-1)}, \quad (i \neq j), \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_0''^{(0)} = \mathbf{R}_0^{-1} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(0)}$, $\mathbf{a}_j''^{(0)} = -\mathbf{R}_0^{-1} \mathbf{R}_j \mathbf{a}_0''^{(0)}$, and $j = 1, 2, \dots, P_1 - 1$. The index of iteration is k and \mathbf{a}_i'' are the $P_2 \times 1$ parameter vectors. The solution of (6)-(7) requires $\mathcal{O}(P_1^2 P_2^2 K)$ multiplications, where K represents the number of iterations to converge to the true parameter values. An additional $P_1 P_2^2$ multiplications are required to compute the initial parameter estimates $\mathbf{a}_j''^{(0)}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, P_1 - 1$. This results

in total multiplications of $\mathcal{O}(P_1^2 P_2^2 K + P_1 P_2^2)$. Depending on the number of iterations required to converge to the true parameters, this total compares with the algorithms of Wax and Kalaith [6] and Akaike [7] which require $\mathcal{O}(P_1^3 P_2^2)$ operations. When large arrays are used this represents a noticeable savings over direct inversion which requires $\mathcal{O}(P_1^3 P_2^3)$ multiplications.

The derivation of the iterative NSHP solution follows a procedure of successive partitioning similar to that of QP support.

4 The Iterative Solution Using Toeplitz Approximation

The discussion of the previous section assumes an autocorrelation matrix with Toeplitz-block-Toeplitz structure. In most cases the autocorrelation matrix must be formed from a limited, and possibly very small, amount of sampled data. In this situation, it is best to use the covariance method to estimate the correlation matrix to reduce the bias in the estimate. However, since this method does not have Toeplitz-block-Toeplitz structure, it is necessary to modify the iterative algorithm described above.

For first quadrant parameter estimates, the covariance estimate \mathbf{R} has the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{0,0} & \mathbf{R}_{0,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{0,P_1-1} \\ \mathbf{R}_{1,0} & \mathbf{R}_{1,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{1,P_1-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{R}_{P_1-1,0} & \mathbf{R}_{P_1-1,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{R}_{P_1-1,P_1-1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

A proven procedure [2] that can be used to form the Toeplitz approximation is to first average the diagonal blocks $\mathbf{R}_{j,j}$, $i = j$ and then form a Toeplitz \mathbf{T} matrix from this averaged block \mathbf{R}_{avg} by averaging its diagonal elements. The diagonal elements of \mathbf{T} can be obtained as follows

$$t(i) = \frac{1}{P_2 - i} \sum_{j=0}^{P_2-i-1} \mathbf{R}_{avg}(i+j, j) \quad (9)$$

where, $i = 0, 1, \dots, P_2 - 1$.

This done, each diagonal block may be written as

$$\mathbf{R}_{j,j} = \mathbf{T} + \Delta_{j,j} \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta_{j,j}$ is the difference between $\mathbf{R}_{j,j}$ and the Toeplitz approximation \mathbf{T} . Combining the successive iterative equations, using the methods described above, results in our solution to the normal equations using the *forward* iterative algorithm for the QP case,

which takes the form

$$\mathbf{a}_0^{(k)} = \mathbf{a}_0^{(0)} - \mathbf{T}^{-1} \Delta_{0,0} \mathbf{a}_0^{(k-1)} - \mathbf{T}^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{P_1-1} \mathbf{R}_{0,i} \mathbf{a}_i^{(k-1)} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_j^{(k)} = -\mathbf{T}^{-1} \Delta_{j,j} \mathbf{a}_j^{(k-1)} - \mathbf{T}^{-1} \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^{P_1-1} \mathbf{R}_{j,i} \mathbf{a}_i^{(k-1)} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_0^{(0)} = \mathbf{T}^{-1} \mathcal{E}^{(0)}$, $\mathbf{a}_j^{(0)} = \mathbf{T}^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{j,0} \mathbf{a}_0^{(0)}$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, P_1-1$. The forward iteration will provide parameters for the first quadrant spectral estimate.

The second quadrant AR parameters $b(i, j)$ may be estimated from the normal equations using the *backward* iterative Toeplitz approximation [8].

5 Data-Adaptive Algorithm

The data-adaptive Toeplitz approximation algorithm is based on the same formulation found in the fixed data case. The algorithm becomes adaptive in nature when the autocorrelation matrix \mathbf{R}_n is updated for each shift n of the filter mask. This permits near real-time computation of AR parameters since estimation begins with the first iteration [8]. As in the fixed data case only the approximated Toeplitz matrix is inverted. Computation time is shortened further by the fact that \mathbf{R}_n is computed only from data covered by the filter mask which amounts to taking the outer product of a $P_1 P_2 \times 1$ vector. The data-adaptive form of the iterative equations are given as

$$\mathbf{a}_j^{(n)} = \mathbf{a}_0^{(0)} \delta(j) - \mathbf{T}^{-1} \Delta_{j,j} \mathbf{a}_j^{(n-1)} - \mathbf{T}^{-1} \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^{P_1-1} \mathbf{R}_{j,i} \mathbf{a}_i^{(n-1)} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_0^{(0)} = \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{s}$, for $j = 0$, and $\mathbf{a}_0^{(0)} = \mathbf{T}_0^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{0,0} \mathbf{a}_0^{(0)}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, P_1-1$. The initial parameter estimates \mathbf{a}_0 are determined for the initial point being estimated and all subsequent parameters \mathbf{a}_j are a function of the parameters computed at the previous mask positions. In the above iterative equations we update the autocorrelation matrix in accordance with the recursive relationship

$$\mathbf{R}_n = \lambda \mathbf{R}_{n-1} + \left(\frac{n-1}{n} \right) \mathbf{x}_n \mathbf{x}_n^T \quad (14)$$

where the $P_1 P_2 \times 1$ vector \mathbf{x}_n is obtained by arranging the 2-D data covered by the filter mask at each shift $n = (n_1, n_2)$ and $0 < \lambda < 1$. The purpose of λ is to nullify the effects of statistical variations in the observed data [8] by lessening the effect of \mathbf{R} computed in the distant past on the current update. The

diagonal blocks of \mathbf{R}_n are then used to obtain \mathbf{T}_n in the same manner used for the fixed data case.

6 Experimental Results

The performance of the data-adaptive Toeplitz approximation algorithm is evaluated by examining the estimated spectral densities computed from the first, second and combined quadrant parameter estimates. The algorithm has been used to estimate the parameters of the sinusoidal input array generated by

$$\begin{aligned} x(n_1, n_2) = & A_1 \cos(2\pi f_{11} n_1 + 2\pi f_{12} n_2) \\ & + A_2 \cos(2\pi f_{21} n_1 + 2\pi f_{22} n_2) \\ & + w(n_1, n_2) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where amplitudes $A_1 = A_2 = \sqrt{2}$ and f_{ij} are normalized frequencies in the range $(0 \leq f_{ij} \leq 0.5)$. The frequencies chosen are $f_{11} = f_{12} = 0.167$ and $f_{21} = f_{22} = 0.333$. Additionally, the data-adaptive algorithm is tested with off-set frequencies to evaluate its performance for that case. The noise term $w(n_1, n_2)$ is zero mean and gaussian with the variance σ_w^2 scaled give a desired signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The SNR (in dB) is defined as [4]

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{A_i^2}{2\sigma_w^2}, \quad (16)$$

where N is the number of sinusoids present and A is the amplitude term. The SNR is varied by holding A_i constant and adjusting the value of σ_w^2 . The algorithm's performance using a 3×3 filter mask is evaluated for various sizes of input arrays and the common regions of support. The covariance method was used to produce the results provided. The data-adaptive algorithm is tested with SNR's of 10 dB and 0 dB. It should be noted that the surface plots in all figures have been rotated 90 degrees to show the separation of the spectral peaks more clearly. Contour plots are provided to better judge the accuracy of the estimates. The axes of the contour plots range from 0-30 which is taken from a 32×32 frequency domain array representing a quadrant of a 64×64 point 2-D FFT output. The 32×32 array covers the frequency range from 0 to π . In the following figures the quadrant estimate giving the best resolution is provided.

The first example demonstrates a unique characteristic of the data-adaptive iterative Toeplitz approximation algorithm. In this example the spectral estimate is computed using a 3×3 filter mask with a 4×4 input array. This means that only *four* elements of the input data are available to the filter to determine

the parameter estimates. This result is of particular interest because the correlation matrix is actually rank deficient, and the problem cannot be solved by direct inversion. Nevertheless, the iterative Toeplitz approximation method does provide a means to compute the estimate. The results are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 4×4 input array (Covariance Method), SNR=10 dB.

As a further test of the algorithm, a signal with offset frequencies $f_{11} = 0.250$, $f_{12} = 0.125$, $f_{21} = 0.300$, and $f_{22} = 0.400$ is generated and processed. The spectral estimates resulting from the computed model parameters are plotted in Figure 2. For this case, the best spectral estimate was obtained using first quadrant support.

The spectral estimates for a signal-to-noise ratio of 0 dB is plotted in Figure 3. The accuracy of the estimates is noticeably degraded in this case. However, a reasonable indication of the signal frequency content can be seen when the combined-quadrant method is used.

The final case using NSHP support is included for completeness. The filter mask had dimensions $P_1 = P_2 = 4$ and $L_2 = -2$. The parameters were estimated for a 16×16 input array. The NSHP spectral estimate is plotted in Figure 4. The resulting spectral estimate shown is quite accurate, but this comes at the cost

Figure 2: 8×8 input array, offset frequencies, (Covariance Method), SNR=10 dB.

Figure 3: 8×8 input array (Covariance Method), SNR=0dB.

Figure 4: 16×16 input array (Covariance Method), SNR=10 dB; nonsymmetric half-plane support.

of greater complexity for the filter. NSHP support may be used as an alternative to combined-quadrant support in some cases.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that high-resolution 2-D spectral estimates can be obtained using the data-adaptive iterative method. The algorithm's performance in a noisy environment is encouraging. This has been accomplished using $\mathcal{O}(P_1^2 P_2^2 K + P_1 P_2^2)$ multiplications, which represents a significant savings over RLS which would require approximately $\mathcal{O}((1.5 P_1 P_2)^2 K + 4.5(P_1 P_2)K)$ multiplications to compute the same parameters. The fact that the algorithm could estimate parameters when the direct inversion method could not be used was noteworthy. In general, the combined-quadrant estimates proved to be the most accurate but this level of complexity is not always required to achieve accurate spectral estimates. Additionally, the iterative methods are guaranteed to converge when the block matrix is symmetric and positive definite. Although other methods may exhibit faster convergence to the true parameters, they do so with greater complexity.

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